

ANALYSIS ON DATA WITH TRIALINDEX 21-30

Number of trials per stimulus mode					
	0	100	140	180	Total
None	32	-	-	-	32
AudioOnly	-	31	24	30	85
VisualsOnly	-	31	32	27	90
Both	-	29	31	28	88
Total	32	91	87	85	295

Stimuli type and performance

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: correctNormalized

ANOVA correctNormalized~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
4.764	0.00294	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.9956651	1.0236729	-1.5267	0.135

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.9818104	1.0244034	-3.8559	0.0001449

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
1.0017013	0.9944518	0.62734	0.531

TukeyHSD			
diff	lwr	upr	p adj

Both-Audio	-0.04517093	-0.0825059	-0.0078359	0.0104594
None-Audio	-0.00100552	-0.0519213	0.0499102	0.9999522
VisualsOnly	-0.04061628	-0.0777469	-0.0034856	0.0257678
None-Both	0.04416541	-0.0065124	0.0948432	0.1119820
VisualsOnly	0.00455465	-0.032249	0.0413583	0.9886706
VisualsOnly	-0.03961076	-0.0901382	0.1019167	0.1809167

Stimuli tempo and performance

Parameter: tempo | Variable: correctNormalized | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo		
F	p	
1.041	0.375	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.214	0.808	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.452	0.638	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.692	0.503	

Stimuli type and time estimation

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception)

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.392	0.759	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
-0.0031414	0.0233673	-0.64068	0.5254

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
-0.0060899	0.0085947	-0.53479	0.5933

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.0059863	-0.0091317	0.55819	0.5772

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.219	0.88	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.1817799	0.1617671	0.72626	0.472

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.1820793	0.1758508	0.35904	0.7199

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.1836409	0.1738916	0.57401	0.5664

Stimuli tempo and time estimation

Parameter: tempo | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception) | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo		
F	p	
0.871	0.456	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.888	0.415	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.086	0.917	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
1.333	0.269	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo		
F	p	
0.32	0.811	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.144	0.866	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.038	0.963	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.173	0.841	

Stimuli type and time judgment

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~classes			
chi-2	df	p	
1.0873	3	0.7801	

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasStimulusTrial			
W	p		
4019.5	0.6689		
mean Has	mean Not		
3.406844	3.46875		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasAudioTrial			
W	p		
9898.5	0.3475		
mean Has	mean Not		
3.369942	3.47541		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasVisualTrial			
W	p		
10789	0.5871		
mean Has	mean Not		
3.432584	3.384615		

Stimuli tempo and time judgment

Parameter: tempo | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo			
chi-2	df	p	
4.6273	3	0.2012	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
2.68	2	0.2619	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
0.68212	2	0.711	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterBOTH]			
chi-2	df	p	
2.6837	2	0.2614	

Correlations time judgment - estimation - performance

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized

PEARSON deltaTimePerception~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.12101282	0.1082594	-0.0060128	0.9181

PEARSON abs(deltaTimePerception)~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1796235	0.04776631	-0.0667958	0.2528

SPEARMAN deltaTimePerception~reportedSpeedPerception			
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SPEARMAN abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedSpeedPerception			
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SPEARMAN correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception			
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rho	p
-0.2020665	0.0004795

rho	p
0.0567543	0.3313

rho	p
0.1759789	0.002418

Confounding effects of fatigue

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized, reportedFatigue

ANOVA correctNormalized~reportedFatigue	
F	p
0.496	0.739

Anova deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue	
F	p
0.9	0.464

Anova abs(deltaPerception)~reportedFatigue	
F	p
1.169	0.325

Spearman correctNormalized~reportedFatigue	
rho	p
0.0117690	0.8405

Spearman deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue	
rho	p
0.0478913	0.4125

Spearman abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue	
rho	p
0.0427839	0.4641

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~reportedFatigue	
rho	p
0.2443037	2.208e-05

Confounding effects of trial index

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), correctNormalized, trialIndex

Pearson correctNormalized~trialIndex		
95% CI	cor	p
-0.21612905; 0.0098042;	-0.1045107	0.07308

Pearson deltaTimePerception~trialIndex		
95% CI	cor	p
-0.0075285; 0.2182975;	0.1067611	0.06708

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~trialIndex		
95% CI	cor	p
-0.0356674; 0.1913266;	0.0788515	0.1768